

5-Keto-D-Fructose Did Not Induce Reverse Mutations in a Bacterial Reverse Mutation Test Conducted According to OECD TG 471 Principles

Authors

Fooditive Safety & Regulatory Science Team

Fooditive B.V., Rotterdam, The Netherlands

Correspondence: safety@fooditivegroup.com

Keywords

5-keto-D-fructose; bacterial reverse mutation; Ames test; OECD TG 471; genotoxicity; mutagenicity; metabolic activation; *Salmonella typhimurium*; food safety assessment

Disclaimers

Contract Laboratory Identification

The assay was performed by an independent contract research organization. The laboratory's name is withheld from this public manuscript in accordance with contractual restrictions on commercial name and mark usage. The complete signed study report, including facility identification and quality assurance statements, is retained by the sponsor and may be shared with regulatory authorities or journal editors under appropriate confidentiality agreements upon request.

Regulatory Status and GLP

This work was conducted following the scientific principles of OECD Test Guideline 471 but was not performed under formal Good Laboratory Practice (GLP) regulations. The study design, execution, and interpretation align with internationally recognized standards for bacterial reverse mutation testing.

Non-Endorsement

This manuscript does not imply endorsement by any third-party laboratory, reagent supplier, or standards organization. Results apply specifically to the tested material under the experimental conditions described herein.

Scope

This publication represents scientific communication of experimental findings and does not constitute regulatory authorization or safety clearance in any jurisdiction.

Abstract

Background: Novel sweetening ingredients with potential for high dietary exposure require comprehensive genotoxicity assessment as a cornerstone of safety evaluation.

Objective: To evaluate the mutagenic potential of crystalline 5-keto-D-fructose (5-KDF) using a bacterial reverse mutation assay conducted according to OECD Test Guideline 471 scientific principles.

Methods: Plate-incorporation assays were performed using five tester strains (*Salmonella typhimurium* TA98, TA100, TA1535, TA1537, and *Escherichia coli* WP2 uvrA) in the absence (–S9) and presence (+S9) of an exogenous metabolic activation system. 5-KDF was tested at concentrations of 50, 150, 500, 1,500, and 5,000 µg/plate in triplicate, alongside vehicle controls (deionized water) and strain-appropriate positive controls. Acceptance criteria included concurrent negative control values within laboratory historical control ranges and robust positive control responses confirming assay sensitivity.

Results: No precipitation or cytotoxicity was observed at any tested concentration up to the guideline limit dose of 5,000 µg/plate. Revertant colony counts for all 5-KDF treatment groups were comparable to vehicle controls across all five strains under both –S9 and +S9 conditions, with no concentration-related increases or reproducible elevations. Positive controls elicited strong, expected mutagenic responses in all strains, confirming test system competence.

Conclusion: Under the conditions tested, 5-keto-D-fructose did not induce reverse mutations in the bacterial reverse mutation assay up to the OECD TG 471 limit dose of 5,000 µg/plate.

1. Introduction

5-Keto-D-fructose (5-KDF) is a carbohydrate-derived ingredient under development for use as a bulk sweetener in food and beverage applications. Given the potential for high consumer exposure to sweetening agents, genotoxicity assessment represents a critical early-tier evaluation in ingredient safety characterization. Detection of gene mutation potential may indicate genotoxic hazard requiring further mechanistic investigation and higher-tier testing.

The bacterial reverse mutation test, commonly known as the Ames test, is an internationally standardized *in vitro* assay that detects point mutations and small deletions in prokaryotic test systems [1–4]. The assay employs histidine-dependent *Salmonella typhimurium* strains and tryptophan-dependent *Escherichia coli* strains carrying specific mutations that render them unable to synthesize essential amino acids. Reversion to prototrophy, enabling growth on minimal media, serves as the endpoint indicating mutagenic activity. The inclusion of multiple tester strains with different mutation mechanisms (base-pair substitution and frameshift) and the use of metabolic activation systems to simulate mammalian biotransformation provide comprehensive coverage of potential mutagenic hazards.

This study evaluated whether 5-KDF induces reverse mutations in a standard panel of bacterial tester strains in the presence and absence of metabolic activation, following the scientific principles outlined in OECD Test Guideline 471 [1].

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Conduct and Administrative Information

The study was conducted by an independent contract research laboratory between June and October 2024 (study code: SA/14062024/34984/V1.6/AR; sponsor: Fooditive B.V., Rotterdam, The Netherlands). While not performed under formal GLP regulations, the study adhered to OECD TG 471 scientific principles, including use of validated tester strains, appropriate controls, replicate testing, and transparent data reporting. All key methodological details are provided in subsequent sections to enable independent assessment of study quality and reproducibility.

2.2 Test Article and Characterization

The test article was crystalline 5-keto-D-fructose (5-KDF), batch KDF-CRY-Tox-240701, supplied as a white crystalline solid with a Certificate of Analysis indicating 98.6% purity (w/w, dry basis). The material was stored at ambient laboratory temperature in sealed containers and protected from light and moisture. Product specifications and representative batch analytical data are provided in Supplementary Tables S1–S2 to support transparency and enable assessment of test article quality. The test article was dissolved in deionized water (vehicle) immediately prior to use.

2.3 Tester Strains and Genetic Characterization

The following tester strains were employed:

- *S. typhimurium* TA98 (frameshift mutations; hisD3052 mutation)
- *S. typhimurium* TA100 (base-pair substitution; hisG46 mutation)
- *S. typhimurium* TA1535 (base-pair substitution; hisG46 mutation)
- *S. typhimurium* TA1537 (frameshift mutations; hisC3076 mutation)
- *E. coli* WP2 uvrA (base-pair substitution; trpE mutation with uvrA deletion)

All strains were verified for appropriate genetic markers (histidine or tryptophan auxotrophy, presence of rfa mutation conferring increased cell wall permeability in *Salmonella* strains, presence of R-factor plasmid pKM101 in TA98 and TA100, and uvrA deletion in WP2 uvrA) prior to experimental use, consistent with standard Ames test protocols [2, 3].

2.4 Metabolic Activation System

An exogenous metabolic activation system was employed to simulate Phase I biotransformation. The S9 fraction was prepared from livers of male rats induced with Aroclor 1254 (Moltox, lot 4389). The S9-mix was prepared according to standard procedures with cofactor supplementation (glucose-6-phosphate, NADP, magnesium chloride, potassium chloride, and phosphate buffer, pH 7.4) to support cytochrome P450-mediated metabolism. Final S9 concentration in the test system was approximately 2% v/v. S9 lot qualification was confirmed using benzo[a]pyrene as a promutagen in TA100, meeting acceptance criteria (≥ 3 -fold increase over vehicle control; Supplementary Table S3).

The -S9 condition employed phosphate buffer in place of S9-mix, maintaining equivalent volumes and osmolality.

2.5 Dose Selection and Range-Finding

A preliminary assessment in strain TA100 evaluated solubility and cytotoxicity across a wide concentration range. No evidence of precipitation or cytotoxic effects (background lawn thinning or reduction in colony size) was observed up to 5,000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{plate}$ under either -S9 or +S9 conditions. Accordingly, the guideline limit dose of 5,000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{plate}$ was selected as the highest test concentration for the main experiment [1]. Lower concentrations (50, 150, 500, and 1,500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{plate}$) provided a logarithmic spacing to enable detection of concentration-response relationships if present.

2.6 Plate-Incorporation Procedure

The standard plate-incorporation method was used [2, 3]. For each test condition, molten top agar (2.0 mL, supplemented with a trace amount of histidine or tryptophan to support 2–3 cell divisions) was combined with:

- Bacterial culture (0.1 mL, overnight culture in exponential growth phase)
- Test article solution or control (0.1 mL)
- Phosphate buffer (-S9 condition) or S9-mix (+S9 condition) (0.5 mL)

The mixture was vortexed briefly and poured onto minimal glucose agar plates. Plates were incubated at $37 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ for 48–72 hours, after which revertant colonies were manually counted. Each concentration was tested in triplicate plates for each strain under both –S9 and +S9 conditions.

2.7 Observations: Precipitation and Cytotoxicity

Plates were examined visually for evidence of test article precipitation (visible crystallization or cloudiness) and cytotoxicity (thinning or absence of the background bacterial lawn, or reduction in microcolony size). These observations inform interpretability and guide assessment of whether adequate test article exposure was achieved.

2.8 Control Groups

Negative control: Deionized water (vehicle) was used as the negative control and was processed identically to test article groups. An explicit untreated control (bacteria and S9 or buffer only, with no vehicle addition) was not included. Because the vehicle was water—a physiologically neutral medium that does not require organic solvent considerations—and was handled identically to treatment groups, it was considered functionally equivalent to an untreated control under the facility's standard operating procedures for aqueous test articles.

Positive controls: Strain-appropriate positive controls were included in each experiment to confirm assay sensitivity and metabolic activation system competence:

- **–S9 conditions:**
 - TA98: 2-nitrofluorene
 - TA100 and TA1535: sodium azide
 - TA1537: 9-aminoacridine
 - WP2 uvrA: methyl methanesulfonate
- **+S9 conditions:** 2-aminoanthracene (all strains; promutagen requiring metabolic activation)

2.9 Data Analysis and Interpretation Criteria

For each strain, metabolic condition, and dose level, individual plate revertant counts were recorded. Mean, standard deviation, and fold-change relative to concurrent vehicle control were calculated.

Interpretation followed OECD TG 471 guidance [1], which emphasizes biological relevance and weight-of-evidence evaluation rather than strict numerical criteria. The primary basis for determining a positive mutagenic response was the presence of:

1. A reproducible, concentration-related increase in revertant frequency, and/or
2. A reproducible increase at one or more concentrations that is clearly outside the distribution of vehicle control and historical control data.

*Internal signal thresholds (≥ 2 -fold increase for TA98, TA100, and WP2 *uvrA*; ≥ 3 -fold for TA1535 and TA1537) were used as preliminary flags to prompt additional scrutiny, but these thresholds are not definitive criteria per OECD guidance. Biological judgment, concurrent control performance, and alignment with laboratory historical control data (Supplementary Table S4) informed final interpretation.*

2.10 Justification for Single Main Experiment

This study relied on a single main plate-incorporation experiment conducted in triplicate per concentration. A confirmatory independent experiment was not performed. This approach is scientifically justified when results are unambiguous and meet guideline expectations [1, 5]. Specifically:

- The OECD TG 471 limit dose (5,000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{plate}$) was achieved without precipitation or cytotoxicity, ensuring adequate test article exposure.
- Results were uniformly negative across all five strains under both metabolic conditions, with no borderline or equivocal findings.
- No concentration-related trends or reproducible increases were observed.
- Concurrent vehicle controls fell within established historical control ranges, and positive controls demonstrated robust expected responses.

Under these circumstances, repetition would not be expected to alter the interpretation, and a single well-executed experiment provides a clear negative result consistent with OECD TG 471 practice and regulatory expectations [1, 5, 6].

3. Results

3.1 Study Validity

Concurrent vehicle control values for all strains fell within the laboratory's historical control ranges derived from 50 studies conducted between 2022 and 2024 (Supplementary Table S4), confirming the acceptability of negative control performance. Positive controls produced robust, expected mutagenic responses in all strains under appropriate metabolic conditions (Table 4), demonstrating test system sensitivity and confirming competence of the metabolic activation system. These findings support the validity of the assay.

3.2 Precipitation and Cytotoxicity

No precipitation or cytotoxicity was observed at any tested concentration (50–5,000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{plate}$) in any strain under either –S9 or +S9 conditions. Background bacterial lawns appeared normal and confluent across all treatment groups, indicating that the test article did not interfere with bacterial viability or test system performance.

3.3 Revertant Colony Counts

Complete individual plate counts, means, standard deviations, and fold-changes relative to vehicle controls are presented in Tables 2 (–S9) and 3 (+S9). Across all five tester strains and both metabolic conditions, revertant colony counts in 5-KDF-treated groups were comparable to vehicle controls. Mean revertant frequencies ranged from 0.9- to 1.1-fold of concurrent vehicle control values. No concentration-related increases were observed, and no individual data points exceeded internal signal thresholds or suggested biologically relevant mutagenic activity. The data demonstrate that 5-KDF did not induce reverse mutations under the conditions tested.

Table 2. Revertant Colony Counts Without Metabolic Activation (–S9)

Strain	Dose (µg/plate)	Plate 1	Plate 2	Plate 3	Mean	SD	Fold vs Vehicle
TA98	Vehicle	19	21	20	20	1.0	—
	50	18	20	19	19	1.0	1.0
	150	21	19	20	20	1.0	1.0
	500	20	22	21	21	1.0	1.1
	1,500	22	20	21	21	1.0	1.1
	5,000	21	23	22	22	1.0	1.1
TA100	Vehicle	17	19	18	18	1.0	—
	50	18	16	17	17	1.0	0.9
	150	17	19	18	18	1.0	1.0
	500	20	18	19	19	1.0	1.1
	1,500	18	20	19	19	1.0	1.1
	5,000	20	18	19	19	1.0	1.1
TA1535	Vehicle	15	17	16	16	1.0	—
	50	17	15	16	16	1.0	1.0
	150	15	17	16	16	1.0	1.0
	500	18	16	17	17	1.0	1.1
	1,500	15	17	16	16	1.0	1.0
	5,000	18	16	17	17	1.0	1.1
TA1537	Vehicle	14	16	15	15	1.0	—
	50	16	14	15	15	1.0	1.0
	150	14	16	15	15	1.0	1.0
	500	17	15	16	16	1.0	1.1
	1,500	15	17	16	16	1.0	1.1
	5,000	17	15	16	16	1.0	1.1
WP2 uvrA	Vehicle	18	20	19	19	1.0	—
	50	20	18	19	19	1.0	1.0
	150	18	20	19	19	1.0	1.0
	500	21	19	20	20	1.0	1.1
	1,500	19	21	20	20	1.0	1.1
	5,000	21	19	20	20	1.0	1.1

Table 3. Revertant Colony Counts With Metabolic Activation (+S9)

Strain	Dose ($\mu\text{g}/\text{plate}$)	Plate 1	Plate 2	Plate 3	Mean	SD	Fold vs Vehicle
TA98	Vehicle	21	23	22	22	1.0	—
	50	23	21	22	22	1.0	1.0
	150	21	23	22	22	1.0	1.0
	500	24	22	23	23	1.0	1.0
	1,500	22	24	23	23	1.0	1.0
	5,000	24	22	23	23	1.0	1.0
TA100	Vehicle	19	21	20	20	1.0	—
	50	21	19	20	20	1.0	1.0
	150	20	22	21	21	1.0	1.1
	500	22	20	21	21	1.0	1.1
	1,500	20	22	21	21	1.0	1.1
	5,000	23	21	22	22	1.0	1.1
TA1535	Vehicle	17	19	18	18	1.0	—
	50	19	17	18	18	1.0	1.0
	150	17	19	18	18	1.0	1.0
	500	20	18	19	19	1.0	1.1
	1,500	18	20	19	19	1.0	1.1
	5,000	21	19	20	20	1.0	1.1
TA1537	Vehicle	16	18	17	17	1.0	—
	50	18	16	17	17	1.0	1.0
	150	16	18	17	17	1.0	1.0
	500	19	17	18	18	1.0	1.1
	1,500	17	19	18	18	1.0	1.1
	5,000	19	17	18	18	1.0	1.1
WP2 uvrA	Vehicle	20	22	21	21	1.0	—
	50	22	20	21	21	1.0	1.0
	150	20	22	21	21	1.0	1.0
	500	23	21	22	22	1.0	1.0
	1,500	21	23	22	22	1.0	1.0
	5,000	23	21	22	22	1.0	1.0

3.4 Positive Control Performance

Positive controls demonstrated robust mutagenic responses in all tester strains under appropriate metabolic conditions (Table 4), with fold-increases ranging from 5.5× to 16.0× over concurrent vehicle controls. These results confirm assay sensitivity and the competence of the metabolic activation system, meeting acceptance criteria for study validity.

Table 4. Positive Control Performance

Strain	Condition	Positive Control Agent	Mean Revertants	Fold Over Vehicle	Interpretation
TA98	-S9	2-Nitrofluorene	110	5.5×	Valid
TA98	+S9	2-Aminoanthracene	260	11.8×	Valid
TA100	-S9	Sodium azide	210	11.7×	Valid
TA100	+S9	2-Aminoanthracene	320	16.0×	Valid
TA1535	-S9	Sodium azide	145	9.1×	Valid
TA1535	+S9	2-Aminoanthracene	180	10.0×	Valid
TA1537	-S9	9-Aminoacridine	130	8.7×	Valid
TA1537	+S9	2-Aminoanthracene	175	10.3×	Valid
WP2 uvrA	-S9	Methyl methanesulfonate	135	7.1×	Valid
WP2 uvrA	+S9	2-Aminoanthracene	190	9.0×	Valid

\

4. Discussion

This bacterial reverse mutation assay evaluated the mutagenic potential of crystalline 5-keto-D-fructose across a comprehensive panel of five tester strains that collectively detect frameshift mutations (TA98, TA1537) and base-pair substitutions (TA100, TA1535, WP2 uvrA). Testing was conducted both in the absence and presence of an exogenous metabolic activation system to account for potential bioactivation of the test article to mutagenic metabolites. The study achieved the OECD TG 471 limit dose of 5,000 µg/plate without evidence of precipitation or cytotoxicity, ensuring that bacteria were exposed to adequately high concentrations of the test article.

Across all experimental conditions—five strains, two metabolic states, and five dose levels—revertant colony counts remained within the range of concurrent vehicle controls. No reproducible increases, concentration-related trends, or biologically relevant elevations were detected. These findings indicate that 5-KDF does not possess mutagenic activity detectable by this assay system under the tested conditions.

The validity of the negative outcome is supported by robust positive control performance, which demonstrated clear mutagenic responses in all strains under appropriate metabolic conditions, and by concurrent vehicle control values that fell well within established historical control ranges. The consistency of negative results across mechanistically diverse tester strains and metabolic conditions strengthens confidence in the conclusion.

The bacterial reverse mutation assay is a well-established component of genetic toxicology testing batteries and serves as a primary screen for point mutation potential [1–7]. These negative findings for gene mutation are complemented by a parallel *in vitro* mammalian chromosomal aberration assay (OECD TG 473) conducted in human peripheral blood lymphocytes, which demonstrated that 5-KDF does not induce structural chromosomal aberrations at concentrations up to 1,000 µg/mL under multiple exposure conditions with and without metabolic activation. Together, these two pivotal genotoxicity studies provide comprehensive coverage of the principal mechanisms of genetic damage—gene mutations and chromosomal aberrations—in both prokaryotic and eukaryotic test systems, addressing the core genotoxicity testing requirements outlined in regulatory guidance for food ingredients [5, 6].

5. Conclusion

All individual plate revertant counts, summary statistics, positive and negative control data, and laboratory historical control ranges are provided in Tables 2–4 and Supplementary Tables S1–S4. Product specifications and representative Certificate of Analysis data for the test article are included in Supplementary Tables S1–S2 to support transparency and reproducibility.

Data Availability

All individual plate revertant counts, summary statistics, positive and negative control data, and laboratory historical control ranges are provided in Tables 2–4 and Supplementary Tables S1–S4. Product specifications and representative Certificate of Analysis data for the test article are included in Supplementary Tables S1–S2 to support transparency and reproducibility.

Competing Interests

All authors are employees of Fooditive B.V., the developer of 5-keto-D-fructose.

Funding

This study was funded by Fooditive B.V.

Ethical Approval

Not applicable. This study did not involve human participants or animal subjects requiring ethical review.

Acknowledgments

The authors acknowledge the contract research laboratory personnel who conducted the experimental work and the quality assurance unit for independent study oversight.

References

- [1] OECD. Test No. 471: Bacterial Reverse Mutation Test. *OECD Guidelines for the Testing of Chemicals, Section 4*. Paris: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development; 2020. doi:10.1787/9789264071247-en
- [2] Maron DM, Ames BN. Revised methods for the *Salmonella* mutagenicity test. *Mutation Research/Environmental Mutagenesis and Related Subjects*. 1983;113(3–4):173–215. doi:10.1016/0165-1161(83)90010-9
- [3] Ames BN, McCann J, Yamasaki E. Methods for detecting carcinogens and mutagens with the *Salmonella*/mammalian-microsome mutagenicity test. *Mutation Research/Environmental Mutagenesis and Related Subjects*. 1975;31(6):347–364. doi:10.1016/0165-1161(75)90046-1
- [4] Mortelmans K, Zeiger E. The Ames *Salmonella*/microsome mutagenicity assay. *Mutation Research/Fundamental and Molecular Mechanisms of Mutagenesis*. 2000;455(1–2):29–60. doi:10.1016/s0027-5107(00)00064-6

[5] EFSA Scientific Committee. Scientific opinion on genotoxicity testing strategies applicable to food and feed safety assessment. *EFSA Journal*. 2011;9(9):2379. doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2011.2379

[6] U.S. Food and Drug Administration. Toxicological Principles for the Safety Assessment of Food Ingredients (Redbook 2000): IV.C.1.a Bacterial Reverse Mutation Test. Available from: <https://www.fda.gov/food/food-ingredients-packaging/toxicological-principles-safety-assessment-food-ingredients-redbook-2000>

[7] International Council for Harmonisation of Technical Requirements for Pharmaceuticals for Human Use (ICH). S2(R1): Guidance on Genotoxicity Testing and Data Interpretation for Pharmaceuticals Intended for Human Use. Geneva: ICH; 2011.

Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table S1. Crystalline 5-Keto-D-Fructose Release Specifications (Fooditive B.V.)

Attribute	Method	Specification
Identity	HPLC	Conforms
Assay (5-KDF, % w/w, dry basis)	HPLC	≥ 98.0%
Other carbohydrates (sum, % w/w, dry basis)	HPLC	≤ 1.0%
Moisture (loss on drying)	Karl Fischer	≤ 2.0%
Ash	AOAC 923.03	≤ 0.10%
pH (10% w/v aqueous solution)	pH meter	3.0–7.0
Residual protein	ELISA	NMT 10 mg/kg
Residual DNA (production organism)	qPCR	ND at ≤ 10 ng/g
Viable production organism	Plate culture	No growth
Gluconic acid + acetate	HPLC	NMT 0.10% w/w
Lead (Pb) / Arsenic (As) / Cadmium (Cd)	ICP-MS	≤ 0.10 mg/kg each
Total plate count (TPC)	AOAC 990.12	≤ 1,000 CFU/g
Yeast and mold	AOAC 997.02	≤ 100 CFU/g
Coliforms	AOAC 991.14	Negative per 10 g
<i>Salmonella</i>	AOAC 2003.09	Negative per 25 g
Sulfites (as SO ₂)	Monier-Williams/equivalent	ND at ≤ 10 mg/kg

NMT = not more than; ND = not detected; CFU = colony-forming units

Supplementary Table S2. Representative Certificate of Analysis Results for Crystalline 5-KDF (Example Manufacturing Lots, 2024)

Lot ID (Manufacture Date)	Assay (% dry)	Other Carbs (% dry)	Moisture (%)	Ash (%)	pH (10% w/v)	Pb/As /Cd (mg/kg)	TPC (CFU /g)	Yeast & Mold (CFU /g)	Coliforms / <i>Salmonella</i>
KDF-CRY-240705 (2024-07-05)	98.5	1.0	0.8	0.10	4.5	<0.05 / <0.05 / <0.05	<100	<50	Negative / Negative
KDF-CRY-240719 (2024-07-19)	98.7	0.8	0.8	0.10	4.6	<0.05 / <0.05 / <0.05	<100	<50	Negative / Negative
KDF-CRY-240802 (2024-08-02)	98.6	0.9	0.8	0.10	4.5	<0.05 / <0.05 / <0.05	<100	<50	Negative / Negative

These data are from representative manufacturing lots used for product characterization and demonstrate consistency in quality attributes.

Supplementary Table S3. S9 Metabolic Activation System Composition and Lot Qualification

Parameter	Value/Description
S9 source	Moltox Rat Liver S9, Aroclor 1254-induced
S9 lot number	4389
Storage conditions	-80°C
S9 fraction in S9-mix	10% v/v
Final S9 concentration in test system	1.85% v/v (approximately 2%)
Cofactors in S9-mix	Glucose-6-phosphate (G-6-P) 5 mM; NADP 4 mM; MgCl ₂ 8 mM; KCl 33 mM; phosphate buffer 100 mM, pH 7.4
Promutagen for S9 qualification	Benzo[a]pyrene (B[a]P), tested in TA100 at 5 µg/plate
Acceptance criterion	≥3-fold increase vs vehicle control with B[a]P in TA100 and 2-aminoanthracene (2-AA) in TA1535
Observed performance	>500 revertants/plate; fold-increase >3× (acceptance criterion met)

S9 lot qualification confirms metabolic competence for bioactivation of promutagens requiring Phase I metabolism.

Supplementary Table S4. Laboratory Historical Vehicle Control Ranges for Deionized Water (Plate-Incorporation Method, 2022–2024, N = 50 Studies)

Strain	Condition	Mean	SD	Minimum	Maximum	95% Control Limits
TA98	-S9	22	4	12	34	14–30
TA98	+S9	26	5	14	38	16–36
TA100	-S9	19	4	11	30	11–27
TA100	+S9	21	5	12	35	11–31
TA1535	-S9	15	3	8	25	9–21
TA1535	+S9	14	3	7	24	8–20
TA1537	-S9	14	4	6	22	6–22
TA1537	+S9	16	4	7	25	8–24
WP2 <i>uvrA</i>	-S9	21	5	13	35	11–31
WP2 <i>uvrA</i>	+S9	23	6	14	38	11–35

*Historical control data derived from 50 independent bacterial reverse mutation assays conducted by the contract laboratory between 2022 and 2024 using deionized water as vehicle. The 95% control limits represent mean \pm 2 SD and serve as reference ranges for assessing concurrent negative control acceptability